

Supporting Information

New Improved Diazo-Transfer Reaction for DNA-Encoded Chemistry and their Potential Application for Macrocyclic DEL-Libraries

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1 Abbreviations

°C	degree Celsius
µm	micrometre
µmol	micromole
A	Adenine
Abu	Aminobutyric acid
Abz	Aminobenzoic acid
Ala	Alanine
aq.	aqua
Ava	Aminovaleric acid
BB	broad band decoupling
br	broad
C	Cytosine
calc.	Calculated
d	<i>Doublet</i>
dd	Doublet of a Doublet
ddd	Doublet of a Doublet of a Doublet
DEPT	Distortionless Enhancement by Polarisation Transfer
DIC	N,N'-Diisopropylcarbodiimide
DMF	Dimethylformamide
DMT-MM	4-(4,6-dimethoxy-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl)-4-methyl-morpholinium chloride
eq	Equivalents
Fmoc	Fluorenylmethoxycarbonyl
G	Guanine
Gln	Glutamine
Gly	Glycine
HOBt	1-Hydroxybenzotriazole hydrate
Hz	<i>Hertz</i>
ISA	Imidazole-1-sulfonyl azide
J	Coupling Constant
l	litre
LC-MS	Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry
Lys	Lysine
m	Multiplet
m/z	mass-to-charge ratio
mg	milligram
ml	millilitre
mm	millimetre
mM	millimolar
PDA	Photodiodearray-Detector
Phe	Phenylalanine
ppm	Parts Per Million
RT	Room temperature
s	<i>Singlet</i>
Sar	Sarcosine
SQ	Single Quadrupol
t	Triplet
T	Thymine
TBTA	Tris[(1-benzyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)methyl]amine)
td	Triplet of a Doublet
Temp.	temperature
t _R	Retention time
Trp	Tryptophan

Tyr
 α
 β
 γ
 δ

Tyrosine
 Alpha
 Beta
 Gamma
 Chemical shift

2 Tables

Table 2.1: Optimizing of the DNA-compatible Diazo-Transfer Reaction with aliphatic (1) and aromatic (2) Amines

Entry ^a	ISA (Eq)	CuSO ₄ (Eq)	Buffer (Mol)	Temp. (°C)	Reaction Time (h)	Conversion Amine 1 to Azide 3 (%) ^b	Conversion Aniline 2 to Azide 4 (%) ^b
1	50	10	Borate (0.5) pH9.4	RT	1	81	2
2	50	10	Borate (0.5) pH9.4	RT	16	100	39
3	50	1	Borate (0.5) pH9.4	RT	16	61	49
4	50	10	NaHCO ₃ (0.2)	RT	1	49	9
5	50	10	NaHCO ₃ (0.2)	RT	16	98	55
6	50	1	NaHCO ₃ (0.2)	RT	16	100	48
7	50	1	NaHCO ₃ (0.2)	60°C	16	93 ^c	50 ^c
8	50	10	K ₂ CO ₃ (0.05)	RT	16	98	96
9	50	1	K ₂ CO ₃ (0.05)	RT	16	7	53

^aAll the reactions were conducted at 0.7 mM in 10 nmol scale; ^bConversion observed by UPLC-MS; ^cDNA degradation observed by mass spectrometry

Table 2.2: Optimizing of the DNA-compatible Diazo-Transfer Reaction with aromatic Amine (2)

eq. Azide	eq. CuSO ₄	Buffer	Temp.	Timepoint for aromatic amine 2 ^a			
				1 day	2 days	3 days	4 days
50	1	NaHCO ₃ 200mM	RT	37	63	79	89
50	0	NaHCO ₃ 200mM	RT	37	62	80	88
50	1	K ₂ CO ₃ 50mM	RT	40	67	84	91
50	0	K ₂ CO ₃ 50mM	RT	24	59	76	87
50	1	Borate 500mM	RT	37	66	80	90
50	0	Borate 500mM	RT	36	63	79	88

Number of experiments n=1; ^aConversion observed by UPLC-MS

3 Materials and Instrumentation

HP-280: Biosearch Technologies PN: 185392 Ref.: SS453295-01

Figure 3.1: Structure of HP-280

ISA*H₂SO₄: 1H-Imidazole -1-sulfonylazide sulfate ABCR PN: AB457437 CAS: 1357503-23-1

Chemicals: The commercial compound and solvent were bought from the following Vendors: Sigma-Aldrich, Bachem, Fluka, Adv. ChemTech, ABCR, Neosystem, VWR and Biotech GmbH. The Fmoc-Amino acids (**Table2 Entry 22, 28, 29, 31**) were made from the Amino acids.

NMR: The off-DNA measurements were carried out by the Analytic department. The measurements were done for ¹H NMR at 600 MHz or 500 MHz, for ¹³C NMR-BB and ¹³C NMR-DEPT at 151 MHz or 126 MHz. DMSO-*d*₆ was used as solvent. ACD/Spectrus Processor 2018.1.1 from Advanced Chemistry Development, Inc. was used for the evaluation.

LC-MS System: I) Waters Acquity UHPLC Plus-System with Xevo Ge-XS TOF MS, PDA, oven (40°C) and automated sample injection ; Mass detection: 300 – 3000 m/z (on-DNA)
II) Waters Acquity UHPLC-MS with PDA and SQ- detector, oven (60°C) and automated sample injection ; Mass detection: 100 – 1000 m/z (off-DNA)
III) Lavomatic HD-3000 preparative HPLC with DAD and fraction collector,

Column: I) Kinetex EVO C18 2.6 μm 50 × 2.1 mm PN: 00B-4725-AN from Phenomenex (on-DNA)
II) Acquity UHPLC BEH C18 1.7 μm, 50 × 2.1 mm PN: 186002350 from Waters (off-DNA)
III) Chromatorex C18, 10 μm 125 × 30 mm (preparative HPLC)

Solvent: I) A: 2.92 mg EDTA, 10 ml HFIP, 1 ml DIPEA in 1 l Millipore water (on-DNA)
 B: 2.92 mg EDTA, 0.75 ml HFIP, 0.375 ml DIPEA in 650 ml Acetonitrile und
 350 ml Millipore Wasser (on-DNA)
 II+III) A: H₂O + 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (w=99%)
 B: Acetonitrile (off-DNA and preparative)

Gradient: I) 0.65 ml/min (on-DNA)
 II) 0.80 ml/min (off-DNA)
 III) 65 ml/min (preparative)

(on-DNA)		(off-DNA)		(preparative)	
min	%B	min	%B	min	%B
0.00	5	0.00	1	0.00	30
0.50	5	1.60	99	2.50	30
3.00	60	2.00	99	8.00	70
3.01	5	2.01	1	8.10	100
3.50	5	2.50	1	10.10	100

3.1 General Procedures

General Procedure 1: Ethanol precipitation (GP1): To the aqueous DNA reaction solutions was added 10% (v/v) of 5 M NaCl, followed by 3 volumes of cold ethanol (-78°C). The suspension was allowed to stand for 30min at -78°C and then centrifuged at 5000 rpm. (>0.15 µmol reaction) or 15000 rpm (≤0.15 µmol reaction) for 15 min at 4 °C. The resulting supernatant was discarded. The pellet was dissolved in water to get same volume as the reaction volume and was freeze-dried or further purified by spin-filtration (GP2). The freeze-dried sample was dissolved in deionized water to get 10 mM solution.

General Procedure 2: Spin-filtration (GP2): The solution from the GP1 was transferred into Amicon Ultra-4 3K Centrifugal-Filter and centrifuged to ¼ of the starting volume. The Centrifugal-Filter was filled twice to the starting volume and centrifuged to ¼ of the starting volume. The solution above the filter was transferred and was freeze-dried. The freeze-dried sample was dissolved in deionized water to get 10 mM solution.

Amide bond formation method with DMT-MM (ABF 1): To a stock solution of **HP-280** (100 µl, 10 mM aq.) was added borate-buffer pH9.5 (900 µl, 500 mM aq.), followed by the addition of a solution of Fmoc-amino acid (100 eq, 250 µl, 400 mM in DMF) the DMT-MM (30 eq, 75 µl, 400 mM aq.). The reaction was allowed to proceed overnight at RT. The DNA was precipitated following the procedure **GP1**. The reaction was analysed by LC-MS.

Amide bond formation method with HOBt/DIC (ABF 2): The **HP-280** (100 µl, 10 mM aq.) was added to borate-buffer pH9.5 (900 µl, 500 mM aq.). The HOBt*H₂O solution (100 eq, 250 µl, 400 mM in DMF), DIC-solution (100 eq, 250 µl, 400 mM in DMF) and Fmoc-amino acid solution (100 eq, 500 µl, 200 mM in DMF) were combined and allowed to stand for 10 min at room temperature and then was added to the HP-280 solution. The reaction was let to proceed

overnight at RT. The DNA was precipitated following the procedure **GP1**. The reaction was analysed by LC-MS.

Fmoc deprotection: The DNA-conjugated Fmoc-amino acid was diluted in water (1 mM) and 10% v/v Piperidine was added for 2 h at room temperature. The DNA was precipitated following the procedure **GP1** and **GP2**.

Optimized Diazo-Transfer Reaction 1 (DTR 1): 1 μ l of DNA-Conjugated amino acid (10mM) was added to 13 μ l premixed solution of Copper(II)sulfate pentahydrate (1 eq, 0.5 μ l, 20 mM aq.), $\text{ISA}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (50 eq, 2.5 μ l, 200 mM aq.) and NaHCO_3 (200 eq, 10 μ l, 200 mM aq.) and mixed. The reaction was allowed to stand overnight at RT. The reaction was analysed by LC-MS.

Optimized Diazo-Transfer Reaction 2 (DTR 2): 1 μ l of DNA-Conjugated amino acid (10 mM) was added to 13 μ l premixed solution of Copper(II)sulfate pentahydrate (10 eq, 0.5 μ l, 20 mM aq.), $\text{ISA}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (50 eq, 2.5 μ l, 200 mM aq.) and K_2CO_3 (50 eq, 10 μ l, 50 mM aq.) and mixed. the reaction was allowed to stand overnight at RT. The reaction was analysed by LC-MS. For the LC-MS 1 μ l of the reaction solution was added to 50 μ l Sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (2 mM aq.) as a copper scavenger. The brown precipitant was centrifuged for 1 min and the supernatant was transferred for LC-MS.

Copper(I)-catalysed intramolecular Alkyne-Azide Cycloaddition “click“ reaction method (CuAAC 1): The DNA Conjugated alkyne-azide (1 μ L, 10 mM aq.) was diluted in phosphate buffer (9 μ L, 500 mM, pH 8). 5 μ l of $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 μ l, 2 eq, 10mM DMF), (+)-sodium *L*-ascorbate (2 μ l, 4 eq, 20 mM aq.) and TBTA (1 μ l, 1 eq, 10 mM DMF) mixture was added and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 16 h at RT. The reaction was analysed by LC-MS.

Copper(I)-catalysed intermolecular Alkyne-Azide Cycloaddition “click“ reaction method (CuAAC 2): The DNA Conjugated alkyne-azide (1 μ L, 10 mM aq.) was diluted in phosphate buffer (9 μ L, 500 mM, pH 8). Fmoc-Propargylglycine (1 μ l, 10 eq, 100 mM DMF) and 5 μ l of $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 μ l, 2 eq, 10mM DMF), (+)-sodium *L*-ascorbate (2 μ l, 4 eq, 20 mM aq.) and TBTA (1 μ l, 1 eq, 10 mM DMF) mixture were subsequently added and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 16 h at RT. The reaction was analysed by LC-MS.

3.2 Chromatograms of DNA-conjugated Amino acids and Azides

3.2.1 6-azidohexanoic acid conjugated with HP280 (2)

6-Aminohexanoic acid conjugated with HP280 (1):

Fmoc-6-Aminohexanoic acid (CAS 88574-06-5) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (100 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 1 μ mol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**:

Figure 3.2: LC-MS chromatogram for compound **1** $t_R = 1,35$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1682,317$ (100%) $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1682,316 for $C_{160}H_{226}N_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

6-Azidohexanoic acid conjugated with HP280 (3, Table 2 Entry 6)

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (1), 10nmol scale).

Figure. 3.3: LC-MS chromatogram of compound 2 $t_R = 1.44$ min TOF-MS-ES $^+$ $m/z = 1690,976$ (100%)
[M-3H] $^{3-}$ (calc. 1690,980 for $C_{160}H_{224}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.2 4-Azidobenzoic Acid conjugated with HP280 (4, Table 2 Entry 20)

6-Aminobenzoic Acid conjugated with HP280 (3):

Fmoc-6-Aminobenzoic acid (CAS 185116-43-2) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (100 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 1 μ mol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**:

4-Azidobenzoic acid conjugated with HP280 (4, Table 2 Entry 20):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (3), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.5: LC-MS chromatogram of compound 4 $t_R = 1.44$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1692,960(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1692,964 for $C_{161}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.3 HP-280 Azide (Table 2 Entry 1)

HP-280 Amine:

Figure 3.6 LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 1 amine** $t_R = 1,31$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1644,624$ (100%) $[M3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1644,622 for C₁₅H₂₁N₅O₁₀P₁₇)

HP-280 Azide (Table 2 Entry 1):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (HP-280), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.7: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 1** $t_R = 1.40$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1653,285$ (100%) $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1653,285 for $C_{154}H_{213}N_{54}O_{101}P_{17}$)

3.2.4 Azido-Gly-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 2)

H-Gly-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-Gly-OH (CAS 29022-11-5) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150mmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**:

Figure 3.8: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 2 amine** $t_R = 1.34$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1663,629(100\%) [M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1663,629 for C₁₅₆H₂₁₈N₅₃O₁₀₂P₁₇)

Azido-Gly-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry2):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 2 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.9: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 3 amine** $t_R = 1,36$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁻ $m/z = 1672,291$ (100%) [$M-3H$]³⁻ (calc. 1672,292 for $C_{156}H_{216}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.5 Azido-β-Ala-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 3)

H-β-Ala-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-β-Ala-OH (CAS 35737-10-1) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μl, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**:

Figure 3.10: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 3 amine** $t_R=1,31\text{min}$ TOF-MS-ESI⁺ $m/z=1668,297(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3$ (calc. 1668,301 for $C_{157}H_{220}N_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido- β -Ala-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 3):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 3 amine), 10nmol scale)-

Figure 3.11: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 1** $t_R = 1,37$ min TOF-MS-ES/ $m/z = 1676,965(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1676,964 for $C_{157}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.6 Azido- γ -Abu-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 4)

H- γ -Abu-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc- γ -Abu-OH (CAS 135112-7-5) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.12: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 4 amine** $t_R = 1,31\text{min}$ TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1672,971(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3-$ (calc. 1672,972 for $C_{159}H_{224}N_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido- γ -Abu-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 4):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 4 amine), 10nmol scale)

Figure 3.13: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 4** $t_R = 1,39$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1681,636(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1681,636 for $C_{158}H_{220}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.7 Azido-5-Ava-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 5)

H-5-Ava-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-5-Ava-OH (CAS 123622-48-0) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.14: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 5 amine** $t_R = 1.43$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1677,643(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3-$ (calc. 1677,644 for C₁₅₉H₂₂₄N₅₃O₁₀₂P₁₇)

Azido-5-Ava-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 5):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 5 amine), 10nmol scale)

Figure 3.15: LC-MS Chromatogram of compound Table 2 Entry 5 $t_R = 1.41$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1686,308(100\%) [M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1686,308 for $C_{159}H_{222}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.8 Azido-Sar-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 7)

H-Sar-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-Sar-OH (CAS 77128-70-2) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.16: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 7 amine** $t_R = 1,34$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1668,301(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3$ (calc. 1668,301 for $C_{161}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

H-Sar-OH conjugated with HP280 after Diazo-Transfer Reaction:

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 7 amine), 10nmol scale)

Figure 3.17: LC-MS Chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 7 amine** after Diazo-Transfer Reaction
 $t_R = 1,34$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1668,299$ (100%) $[M-3H]^{\beta-}$ (calc. 1668,301 for $C_{161}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.9 Azido-Ala-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 8)

H-Ala-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-Ala-OH (CAS 35661-39-3) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.18: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 8 amine** $t_R = 1,34$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1668,301(100\%) [M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1668,301 for $C_{157}H_{220}N_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-Ala-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 8):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 8 amine), 10nmol scale)

Figure 3.19: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 8** $t_R = 1,38$ min TOF-MS-ES1
 $m/z = 1676,964(100\%) [M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1674,964 for $C_{157}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.10 Azido- α -methylalanine conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 9)

H- α -Methylalanine conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc- α -Methylalanine (CAS 94744-50-0) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.20: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 9 amine** $t_R = 1.35$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1692,964(100\%) [M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1692,964 for $C_{158}H_{222}N_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido- α -methylalanin conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 9):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 9 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.21: LC-MS chromatogram of compound Table 2 Entry 9 $t_R = 1,41$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁻ $m/z = 1681,634(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1681,636 for $C_{158}H_{220}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.11 Azidocycloleucine conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 10)

Cycloleucine conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-Cycloleucine (CAS 52-52-8) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.22: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 10 amine** $t_R = 1,37$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1681,644(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3$ (calc. 1681,644 for $C_{161}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azidocycloleucine conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 10):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 10 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.23: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 10** $t_R = 1,45$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1690,304(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1690,308 for $C_{161}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.12 Azido-Propargylglycine conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 11)

Propargylglycine conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-Propargylglycine (CAS 198561-07-8) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.24: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 11 amine** $t_R = 1,37$ min TOF-MS-ES/ $m/z = 1676,301(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1676,301 for $C_{159}H_{220}N_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-Propargylglycin conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 11):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 11 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.25: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 11** $t_R = 1,39$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁺ $m/z = 1684,963(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3$ (calc. 1684,964 for $C_{159}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.13 Azido-Lys(Alloc)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 12)

H-Lys(Alloc)-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-Lys(Alloc)-OH (CAS 146982-27-6) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.26: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 14** $t_R = 1,39$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1715,327(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{\ominus}$ (calc. 1715,327 for $C_{164}H_{231}N_{54}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Azido-Lys(Alloc)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 12):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 12 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.27: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 12 amine** $t_R = 1,45$ min TOF-MS-ES⁺ $m/z = 1723,986$ (100%) $[M-3H]^3+$ (calc. 1723,990 for $C_{164}H_{229}N_{56}O_{104}P_{17}$)

3.2.14 Azido-Gln-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 13)

H-Gln-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-Gln-OH (CAS 71989-20-3) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.28: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 12** $t_R = 1,33$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁺ m/z = 1723,986 (100%) [M-3H]³⁺ (calc. 1723,990 for C₁₆₄H₂₂₉N₅₆O₁₀₄P₁₇)

Azido-Gln-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 13):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 13 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.29: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 13 amine** $t_R = 1,33$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁻ $m/z = 1695,970$ (100%) $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1695,971 for $C_{159}H_{223}N_{56}O_{103}P_{17}$)

3.2.15 Azido-Phe(4-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 14)

H-Phe(4-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-Phe(4-Br)-OH (CAS 198561-04-5) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.30: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 14 amine** $t_R = 1,45$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁺ $m/z = 1719,946(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1719,947 for $C_{163}H_{223}BrN_5O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-Phe(4-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 14):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 14 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.31: LC-MS chromatogram of compound Table 2 Entry 14 $t_R = 1.50$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1728,610(100\%) [M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1728,611 for $C_{163}H_{221}BrN_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.16 Azido-Tyr-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 15)

H-Tyr-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-Tyr-OH (CAS 92954-90-0) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.32: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 15 amine** $t_R = 1.46$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁺ $m/z = 1692,964(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1692,964 for $C_{161}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-Tyr-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 15):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 15 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.33: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 15** $t_R = 1,40$ min TOF-MS-ESI
 $m/z = 1707,639(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1707,639 for $C_{161}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.17 Azido-Phe(4-N-Boc)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 16)

H-Phe(4-N-Boc)-OH conjugated with HP280

Fmoc-Phe(4-N-Boc)-OH (CAS 174132-31-1) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.34: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 16 amine** $t_R = 1.46$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1731.995$ (100%) $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1731.999 for $C_{168}H_{233}N_{54}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Azido-Phe(4-N-Boc)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 16)

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 16 amine), 10nmol scale).

3.2.18 Boc-Phe(4-azido)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 17)

Boc-Phe(4-NH₂)-OH conjugated with HP280

Boc-Phe(Fmoc)-OH (CAS 114346-31-5) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 µl, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.36: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 17 amine** $t_R = 1.70$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1806.019(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3-$ (calc. 1806.022 for $C_{183}H_{243}N_{54}O_{106}P_{17}$)

Boc-Phe(4-Azido)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 17)

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 17 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.37: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 17** $t_R = 1.53$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1740.660$ (100%) $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1740.662 for C₁₆₈H₂₃₁N₅₆O₁₀₄P₁₇)

3.2.19 Azido-Trp-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 18)

H-Trp-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-Trp-OH (CAS 65737-15-6) was conjugated using general method **ABF 1** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.38. LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 18 amine** $t_R = 1,40$ min TOF-MS-ESI/ $m/z = 1706,646(100\%) [M-3H]^3-$ (calc. 1706,648 for $C_{165}H_{225}N_{54}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-Trp-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 18):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 18 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.39: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 18** $t_R = 1.45$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1715,307(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1715,311 for $C_{165}H_{223}N_{56}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.20 3-(Azidomethyl)benzoic acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 19)

3-(Aminomethyl)benzoic acid conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-3-(Aminomethyl)benzoic acid (CAS155369-11-2) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.40. LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 19 amine** $t_R = 1,46$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁺ $m/z = 1688,973(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1688,972 for $C_{162}H_{222}N_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3-(Azidomethyl)benzoic acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 19):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 19 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.41: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 19** $t_R = 1.46$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1697,633(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1697,636 for C₁₆₂H₂₂₀N₅₅O₁₀₂P₁₇)

3.2.21 Azido-3-Abz-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 21)

H-3-Abz-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-3-Abz-OH (CAS 185116-42-1) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.42: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 21 amine** $t_R = 1,39$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1684,299(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1684,301 for $C_{161}H_{220}N_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-3-Abz-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 21):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 21 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.43: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 21** $t_R = 1,46$ min TOF-MS-ES/ $m/z = 1692,964$ (100%) $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1692,964 for C₁₆₁H₂₁₈N₅₅O₁₀₂P₁₇)

3.2.22 Azido-2-Abz-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 22)

H-2-Abz-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-2-Abz-OH (CAS 150256-42-1) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.44: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 22 amine** $t_R = 1,41$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁺ $m/z = 1684,300(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3+$ (calc. 1684,301 for $C_{159}H_{220}N_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-2-Abz-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 22):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 22 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.45: LC-MS chromatogram of compound Table 2 Entry 22 $t_R = 1.45$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1692,963(100\%) [M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1692,964 for $C_{161}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.23 Azido-3-Abz(4-F)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 23)

3-Abz(4-F)-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-3-Abz(4F)-OH (CAS 1339407-92-9) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.46: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 23 amine** $t_R = 1,39$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁺ $m/z = 1690,294(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1690,297 for C₁₆₁H₂₁₉FN₅₃O₁₀₂P₁₇)

Azido-3-Abz(4-F)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 23):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 23 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.47: LC-MS chromatogram of compound Table 2 Entry 23 $t_R = 1.47$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1698,960(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3$ calc. 1698,961 for $C_{161}H_{217}FN_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$

3.2.24 Azido-3-Abz(6-Cl)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 24)

H-3-Abz(6-Cl)-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-3-Abz(6-Cl)-OH (CAS 186320-11-6) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.48: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 24 amine** $t_R = 1,43$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1695,621(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1695,621 for $C_{161}H_{219}ClN_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-3-Abz(6-Cl)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 24)

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 24 amine), 10nmol scale).

3.2.25 Azido-2-Abz(6-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 25)

H-2-Abz(6-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-2-Abz(6-Br)-OH (CAS 20776-48-1 free amine) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.50: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 25 amine** $t_R = 1.43$ min TOF-MS-ES⁺ $m/z = 1710,603(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1710,604 for $C_{161}H_{219}BrN_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-2-Abz(6-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 25):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 25 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.51: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 25** $t_R = 1,50$ min TOF-MS-ES⁺ $m/z = 1719,363(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3$ (calc. 1719,367 for C₁₆₁H₂₁₇BrN₅₅O₁₀₂P₁₇)

3.2.26 H-2-Abz(4-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 26)

H-2-Abz(4-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280

Fmoc-2-Abz(4-Br)-OH (CAS 1340472-73-2) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.52: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 26 amine** $t_R = 1.46$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1710.602$ (100%) $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1710.604 for $C_{161}H_{219}BrN_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-2-Abz(4-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 26)

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 25 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.53: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 25** $t_R = 1.49$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1719.265(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1719.267 for $C_{161}H_{217}BrN_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.27 H-3-Abz(3-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 27)

H-3-Abz(3-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280

Fmoc-3-Abz(3-Br)-OH (CAS 1696643-67-0) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.54: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 27 amine** $t_R = 1.42$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1710.605(100\%) [M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1710.604 for $C_{161}H_{219}BrN_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-3-Abz(3-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 27)

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 25 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.55: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 27** $t_R = 1.49$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1719.264(100\%) [M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1719.267 for $C_{161}H_{217}BrN_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.28 H-3-Abz(2-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 28)

H-3-Abz(2-Br)-OH conjugated

Fmoc-3-Abz(2-Br)-OH (CAS 16889-61-4 free amine) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.56: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 28 amine** $t_R = 1.37$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1710.601(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3$ (calc. 1710.604 for $C_{161}H_{219}BrN_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-3-Abz(2-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 28)

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 25 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.57: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 28** $t_R = 1.45$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁻ $m/z = 1719.263(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1719.267 for C₁₆₁H₂₁₇BrN₅₅O₁₀₂P₁₇)

3.2.29 H-4-Abz(2-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 29)

H-4-Abz(2-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280

Fmoc-4-Abz(2-Br)-OH (CAS 2486-52-4 free amine) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.58: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 29 amine** $t_R = 1.40$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1710.6015$ (100%) [$M-3H$] $^{3-}$ (calc. 1710.604 for $C_{161}H_{219}BrN_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

Azido-4-Abz(2-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 29)

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 25 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.59: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 29** $t_R = 1.45$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁻ $m/z = 1719.266(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{-3}$ (calc. 1719.267 for C₁₆₁H₂₁₇BrN₅₅O₁₀₂P₁₇)

3.2.30 H-4-Abz(3-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 30)

H-4-Abz(3-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280

Fmoc-4-Abz(3-Br)-OH (CAS 1339688-25-3) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.60: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 30 amine** $t_R = 1.41$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1710.598(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^+$ calc. 1710.604 for $C_{161}H_{219}BrN_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$

Azido-4-Abz(3-Br)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 30)

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 30 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.61: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 30** $t_R = 1.42$ min TOF-MS-ESI
 $m/z = 1719.264(100\%) [M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1719.267 for $C_{161}H_{217}BrN_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.31 4-Azido-Abz(2-I)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 31)

H-4-Abz(2-I)-OH conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-4-Abz(2-I)-OH (CAS2122-63-6 free amine) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.62: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 31 amine** $t_R = 1,43$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1764,318(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3-$ (calc. 1764,320 for $C_{161}H_{219}IN_{53}O_{102}P_{17}$)

4-Azido-Abz(2-I)-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 31):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 31 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.63: LC-MS chromatogram of compound Table 2 Entry 31 $t_R = 1,50$ min TOF-MS-ES $^+$ $m/z = 1734,924$ (100%) $[M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1734,930 for $C_{161}H_{217}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.32 5-Azidooncotinic acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 32)

5-Aminonicotinic acid conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-5-Aminonicotinic acid (CAS 457100-77-5) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.64: : LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 32 amine** $t_R = 1,36$ min TOF-MS-ES/
 $m/z = 1684,632(100\%) [M-3H]^3$ (calc. 1684,632 for $C_{160}H_{219}N_{54}O_{102}P_{17}$)

5-Azidonicotinic acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 32):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 32 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.65: LC-MS chromatogram of compound Table 2 Entry 32 $t_R = 1.42$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1693,294(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1693,296 for $C_{160}H_{217}N_{56}O_{104}P_{17}$)

3.2.33 3-Azidopicolinic acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 33)

3-Aminopicolinic acid conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-3-Aminopicolinic acid (CAS 1567020-33-0) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.66: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 33 amine** $t_R = 1,36$ min TOF-MS-ES- $m/z = 1684,632(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1684,632 for $C_{160}H_{219}N_{54}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3-Azidopicolin acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 33)

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 33 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.67: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 33** $t_R = 1,41$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁻ $m/z = 1693,290(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1693,296 for $C_{160}H_{217}N_{56}O_{104}P_{17}$)

3.2.34 6-Azidonicotinic acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 34)

6-Aminonicotinic acid conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-6-Aminonicotinic acid (CAS3167-49-5 free amine) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 µl, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.68: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 34 amine** $t_R = 1,38$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1684,632$ (100%) $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1684,632 for $C_{160}H_{219}N_{54}O_{102}P_{17}$)

6-Azidonicotinic acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 34):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 34 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.69: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 34** $t_R = 1,38$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1693,296(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1693,296 for $C_{160}H_{217}N_{56}O_{104}P_{17}$)

3.2.35 2-Azidopyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 35)

2-Aminopyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid conjugated with HP280:

2-Aminopyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid (CAS 3167-50-8) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.70: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 35 amine** $t_R = 1,37$ min TOF-MS-ES⁺ $m/z = 1684,963(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3+$ (calc. 1684,964 for $C_{159}H_{218}N_{55}O_{102}P_{17}$)

2-Azidopyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 35):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 35 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.71: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 35** $t_R = 1,34$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1684,624(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (starting material) (calc. 1693,628 for $C_{159}H_{216}N_{57}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.2.36 4-Azido-1-*H*-pyrazole-1-acetic acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 36)

4-Amino-1-*H*-pyrazole-1-acetic acid conjugated with HP280:

Fmoc-4-Amino-1-*H*-pyrazole-1-acetic acid (CAS 1341762-24-0) was conjugated using general method **ABF 2** (15 μ l, 10 mM HP-280, 150 nmol scale) and purified with general purification method **GP1**. The Fmoc deprotection was carried out using general method for Fmoc deprotection and was purified using the methods **GP1** and **GP2**.

Figure 3.72: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 36** amine $t_R = 1,35$ min TOF-MS-ES^t $m/z = 1684,632(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^3-$ (calc. 1684,632 for $C_{160}H_{219}N_{54}O_{102}P_{17}$)

4-Azido-1-*H*-pyrazol-1-acetic acid conjugated with HP280 (Table 2 Entry 36):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 2 Entry 36 amine), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.73: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 2 Entry 36** $t_R = 1.41$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1694.298$ (100%) $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1694.299 for $C_{159}H_{218}N_{57}O_{102}P_{17}$)

3.3 Chromatograms of DNA-conjugated Tripeptides and Cyclization

The following tripeptides were built with the following methods:

TABLE 3: Overview of the Macrocycle Syntheses on-DNA

Entry	AA1	AA2	AA3	Ring size of cyclized product 7
1	Pra	L-Phe	3-Abz	n = 13
2	Pra	L-Phe	2-Abz	n = 12
3	Pra	L-Phe	β -Ala	n = 12
4	Pra	L-Trp	β -Ala	n = 12
5	Pra	L-Trp	Gly	n = 11
6	Pra	L-Trp	γ -Abu	n = 13
7	Pra	β -Ala	β -Ala	n = 13
8	Pra	β -Ala	γ -Abu	n = 14
9	Pra	β -Ala	3-Abz	n = 14

The DNA conjugated Pra-OH (**Table 2 Entry 11**) was split into three portions of 114 μ l (10mM aq.). The second amino acids (Fmoc-Phe-OH, Fmoc-Trp-OH and Fmoc- β -Ala-OH) were coupled with the general method **ABF 1** and followed by purification method **GP 1**. The Fmoc-groups were deprotected by the general deprotection method and then purified by general methods **GP 1** and **GP 2**.

The three dipeptides described above were each split into three portions of 38 μ l (10mM aq.). The third amino acids (Fmoc-3-Abz-OH or Fmoc-2-Abz-OH) was coupled using the **ABF 2** method and (Fmoc- β -Ala-OH, Fmoc-Gly-OH or Fmoc- γ -Abu-OH) was coupled using the general method **ABF 1** followed by general method **GP 1**. The Fmoc-groups were deprotected with the general deprotection method and then purified by general method **GP 1** and **GP 2**.

3.3.1 [cyclo-3-Abz-Phe-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 1)

H-3-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 1 amine):

Figure 3.74: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 1 amine** $t_R = 1.46$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1765.000(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1765.002 for $C_{175}H_{234}N_{55}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Azido-3-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 1 Azide):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 2(15 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 1 amine), 150nmol scale) followed by general method GP 1.

Figure 3.75: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 1 azide** $t_R = 1.55$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁻ $m/z = 1773.663$ (100%) $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1773.666 for $C_{171}H_{232}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Azido-3-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 2. Synthesis (Table 3 Entry 1 Azide):

Compound 15 was conjugated using general method ABF 1 (10 μ l, 10 mM of (HP-280), 100nmol scale) followed by general method GP 1.

Figure 3.76: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 1 azide** $t_R = 1.55$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1773.662(100\%) [M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1773.666 for $C_{171}H_{232}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

[cyclo-3-Abz-Phe-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 1 Cyclo-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 1 method (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 1 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.77: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 1 cyclo-triazole** $t_R = 1,54+1,56$ min
TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1757.660(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1757.666 for $C_{171}H_{232}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Linear Triazole of Azido-3-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 1 Linear-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 2 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 1 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.78: LC-MS Chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 1 linear triazole** $t_R = 1,48$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1885.370(100\%) [M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1885.371 for C₁₉₅H₂₄₉N₅₈O₁₀₈P₁₇)

Figure 3.79: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 1** cyclo-triazole reaction with Fmoc-Pra-OH

3.3.2 [cyclo-2-Abz-Phe-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 2)

Azido-2-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 2 Azide):

Compound 14 was coupled with **ABF 1** method (10 µl, 10 mM of **(HP-280)**, 100nmol scale) followed by **GP 1**.

Figure 3.80: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 2 azide** $t_R = 1.57$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1773.665(100\%) [M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1773.666 for C₁₇₅H₂₃₂N₅₇O₁₀₄P₁₇)

[cyclo-2-Abz-Phe-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 1 Cyclo-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method **CuAAC 1** method (1 µl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 2 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.81: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 2 cyclo-triazole** $t_R = 1,48$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1773.664(100\%) [M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1773.666 for $C_{175}H_{232}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Linear Triazole of Azido-2-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 2 Linear-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 2 (1 µl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 2 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.82: LC-MS Chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 2 linear-triazole** $t_R = 1,48$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1884.367(100\%) [M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1884.371 for $C_{195}H_{249}N_{58}O_{108}P_{17}$)

3.3.3 [cyclo-β-Ala-Phe-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 3)

H-β-Ala-Phe-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 3 Amine)

Figure 3.83: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 3 amine** $t_R = 1.63$ min TOF-MS-ESI/ $m/z = 1823.022(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1823.025 for $C_{186}H_{244}N_{55}O_{106}P_{17}$)

Azido-β-Ala-Phe-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 3 Azide):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (15 μl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 3 amine), 150nmol scale) followed by GP 1.

Figure 3.84: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 3 Azide** $t_R = 1.48$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1757.664(100\%) [M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1757.666 for $C_{171}H_{232}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

[cyclo-β-Ala-Phe-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 3 Cyclo-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 1 (1 μl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 3 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.85: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 3 cyclo-triazole** $t_R = 1,41$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1757.664(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1757.666 for $C_{171}H_{232}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Linear triazole of Azido-β-Ala-Phe-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 3 Linear-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 2 (1 μl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 3 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.86: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 3 linear-triazole** $t_R = 1,60$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1869.367(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1869.371 for $C_{171}H_{232}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

3.3.5 [cyclo-β-Ala-Trp-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 4)

H-β-Ala-Trp-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 4 Amine):

Figure 3.87: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 4 amine** $t_R=1.39$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1762.003(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1762.006 for $C_{173}H_{235}N_{56}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Azido-β-Ala-Trp-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 4 Azide):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (15 μl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 4 amine), 150nmol scale) followed by general method GP 1.

Figure 3.88: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 4 azide** $t_R = 1.48$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1770.667(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1770.670 for $C_{173}H_{233}N_{58}O_{104}P_{17}$)

[cyclo-β-Ala-Trp-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 4 Cyclo-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 1 (1 μl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 4 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.89: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 4 cyclo-triazole** $t_R = 1,48$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1770.666(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1770.670 for $C_{173}H_{233}N_{58}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Linear Triazole of Azido- β -Ala-Trp-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 4 Linear-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 2 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 4 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.90: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 4 linear-triazole** $t_R = 1.48$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1882.367(100\%) [M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1882.375 for C₁₉₃H₂₅₀N₅₉O₁₀₈P₁₇)

3.3.6 [cyclo-Gly-Trp-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 5)

H-Gly-Trp-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 5 Amine):

Figure 3.91: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 5 amine** $t_R = 1,39$ min TOF-MS-ES/ $m/z = 1757.331(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1757.334 for $C_{172}H_{233}N_{56}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Azido-Gly-Trp-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 5 Azide):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (15 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 5 amine), 150nmol scale) followed by general method GP 1.

Figure 3.92: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 5 azide** $t_R = 1.44$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1765.994(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1765.998 for $C_{171}H_{231}N_{58}O_{104}P_{17}$)

[cyclo-Gly-Trp-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 5 Cyclo-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 5 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.93: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 5 cyclo-triazole**, TOF-MS-ESI⁺ m/z = 1884.367(100%) [M-3H]³⁺ (calc. 1884.371 for C₁₇₁H₂₃₂N₅₇O₁₀₄P₁₇)

Linear Triazole of Azido-Gly-Trp-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 5 Linear-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 2 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 5 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.94: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 5 linear triazole** $t_R = 1,48$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1877.697(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1877.703 for C₁₉₂H₂₄₈N₅₉O₁₀₈P₁₇)

Figure 3.95: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 5 cyclo-triazole** reaction with Fmoc-Pra-OH

3.3.7 [cyclo- γ -Abu-Trp-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 6)

H- γ -Abu-Trp-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 6 Amine):

Figure 3.96: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 6 amine** $t_R = 1.39$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1766.676(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1766.678 for $C_{174}H_{237}N_{56}O_{104}P_{17}$)

[cyclo- γ -Abu-Trp-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 6 Cyclo-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 6 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.98: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 6 cyclo-triazole** $t_R = 1,42$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1775.339(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1775.341 for $C_{174}H_{235}N_{58}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Linear Triazole of Azido- γ -Abu-Trp-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 6 Linear-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 2 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 6 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.99: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 6 linear-triazole** $t_R = 1,61$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1887.037(100\%) [M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1887.047 for $C_{199}H_{252}N_{59}O_{108}P_{17}$)

Figure 3.100: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 6** *cyclo-triazole* reaction with *Fmoc-Pra-OH*

3.3.8 [cyclo-βAla-βAla-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 7)

H-β-Ala-β-Ala-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 7 Amine):

Figure 3.101: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 7 amine** $t_R = 1,34$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁺ $m/z = 1723.659(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^+$ (calc. 1723.659 for C₁₆₅H₂₃₀N₅₅O₁₀₄P₁₇)

[cyclo-β-Ala-β-Ala-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 7 Cyclo-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 1 (1 μl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 7 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.103: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 7 cyclo-triazole** $t_R=1,35$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1732.323(100\%) [M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1732.322 for $C_{165}H_{228}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Linear Triazole of Azido-β-Ala-β-Ala-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 7 Linear-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 2 (1 µl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 7 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.104: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 7 linear-triazole** $t_R = 1,54$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁻ $m/z = 1884.023(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1884.027 for C₁₈₅H₂₄₅N₅₈O₁₀₈P₁₇)

Figure 3.105: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 7** cyclo-triazole reaction with Fmoc-Pra-OH

Azido- γ -Abu- β -Ala-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 8 Azide):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (15 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 8 amine), 150nmol scale) followed by general method GP 1.

Figure 3.107: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 8 azide** $t_R = 1,40$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁻ $m/z = 1736.994(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1736.994 for $C_{166}H_{230}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

[cyclo- γ -Abu- β -Ala-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 8 Cyclo-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 1 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 8 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.108: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 8 cyclo-triazole** $t_R = 1,36$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1736.993(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1736.994 for $C_{166}H_{230}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Linear Triazole of Azido- γ -Abu- β -Ala-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 8 Linear-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 2 (1 μ l, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 8 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.109: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 8 linear-triazole** $t_R = 1,55$ min TOF-MS-ES⁺ $m/z = 1848.692$ (100%) [$M-3H$]³⁺ (calc. 1848.699 for C₁₈₆H₂₄₇N₅₈O₁₀₈P₁₇)

Figure 3.110: LC-MS Chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 8** cyclo-triazole reaction with Fmoc-Pra-OH

3.3.10 [cyclo-3-Abz-β-Ala-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 9)

H-3-Abz-β-Ala-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 9 Amine):

Figure 3.111: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 9 amine** $t_R = 1,38$ min TOF-MS-ESI- $m/z = 1739.658(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{3-}$ (calc. 1739.659 for $C_{169}H_{230}N_{55}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Azido-3-Abz-β-Ala-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 9 azide):

The reaction was carried out by using the general method DTR 1 (15 µl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 9 amine), 150nmol scale) followed by general method GP 1.

Figure 3.112: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 9 azide** $t_R = 1.44$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁻ $m/z = 1748.320(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^{-}$ (calc. 1748.322 for $C_{169}H_{228}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

[cyclo-3-Abz-β-Ala-Pra]-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 9 Cyclo-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 1 (1 μl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 9 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.113: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 9 cyclo-triazole** $t_R = 1,48$ min TOF-MS-ESI $m/z = 1748.319(100\%)$ $[M-3H]^-$ (calc. 1748.322 for $C_{169}H_{228}N_{57}O_{104}P_{17}$)

Linear Triazole of Azido-3-Abz-β-Ala-Pra-OH conjugated with HP280 (Table 3 Entry 9 Linear-Triazole):

The reaction was carried out using method CuAAC 2 (1 μl, 10 mM of (Table 3 Entry 9 azide), 10nmol scale).

Figure 3.114: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 9 linear-triazole** $t_R = 1,57$ min TOF-MS-ESI⁻ $m/z = 1860.032(100\%) [M-3H]^{-3}$ (calc. 1860.028 for $C_{189}H_{245}N_{58}O_{108}P_{17}$)

Figure 3.115: LC-MS chromatogram of compound **Table 3 Entry 9** cyclo-triazole reaction with Fmoc-Pra-OH

3.4 Methods and NMRs of Off-DNA Compounds (8-19)

3.4.1 Azido-Gly-Phe-Pra-NH₂ (12)

H-Gly-Phe-Pra-NH₂×TFA (8):

Figure 3.116: ¹H-NMR of H-Gly-Phe-Pra-NH₂×TFA (8)

Figure 3.117: ^{13}C -NMR-BB (top) and ^{13}C -NMR-DEPT (bottom) of *H*-Gly-Phe-Pra- NH_2 xTFA (**8**)

Compound delivered by Peptide Synthesis Laboratory:

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 2.47 (dd, *J*=7.63, 2.67 Hz, 1 H), 2.55 (dd, *J*= 5.72, 2.67 Hz, 1 H), 2.74 (dd, *J*= 13.73, 9.92 Hz, 1 H), 2.88 (t, *J*= 2.67 Hz, 1 H), 3.05 (dd, *J*= 14.11, 4.20 Hz, 1 H), 3.41 (d, *J*= 16.02 Hz, 1 H), 3.55 (d, *J*= 16.02 Hz, 1 H), 4.34 (td, *J*= 7.72, 5.91 Hz, 1 H), 4.69 - 4.73 (m, 1 H), 7.17 - 7.24 (m, 2 H), 7.24 - 7.29 (m, 4 H), 7.38 (s, 1 H), 7.94 (br s, 3 H), 8.46 (d, *J*= 8.01 Hz, 1 H), 8.65 (d, *J*= 8.39 Hz, 1 H);

¹³C NMR-BB (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.89 (s, 1 C), 37.98 (s, 1 C), 40.05 (s, 1 C), 51.53 (s, 1 C), 53.94 (s, 1 C), 73.10 (s, 1 C), 80.60 (s, 1 C), 113.65 - 121.13 (m, 1 C), 126.43 (s, 1 C), 128.13 (s, 2 C), 129.28 (s, 2 C), 137.44 (s, 1 C), 157.84 (d, *J*= 30.52 Hz, 1 C), 165.66 (s, 1 C), 170.71 (s, 1 C), 171.29 (s, 1 C);

¹³C NMR-DEPT (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.89 (s, 1C), 37.98 (s, 1 C), 51.53 (s, 1 C), 53.94 (s, 1 C), 73.10 (s, 1 C), 80.60 (s, 1 C), 126.43 (s, 1 C), 128.13 (s, 2 C), 129.28 (s, 2 C);

MS ES+ *m/z* = 317.228 [M+H]⁺ (C₁₆H₂₀N₄O₅).

Azido-Gly-Phe-Pra-NH₂ (12):

Figure 3.118: ¹H-NMR of Azido-Gly-Phe-Pra-NH₂ (12)

Figure 3.119: ^{13}C -NMR-BB (top) and ^{13}C -NMR-DEPT (bottom) of Azido-Gly-Phe-Pra- NH_2 (**12**)

H-Gly-Phe-Pra-NH₂ x TFA (**8**) (1 eq, 50 mg, 116 μmol) was dissolved in NaHCO₃ (7 eq, 4.07 ml, 200 mM aq.) and ISAxH₂SO₄ (2.5 eq, 563 μl, 500 mM aq.) and copper(II)sulfate pentahydrate (0.01 eq, 56.2 μl, 20 mM aq.) was added. The reaction was stirred for 16 h at room temperature and resulted in formation of a precipitate. The reaction was controlled by LC-MS. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and dissolved in methanol. The LC-MS showed clean product (**12**). The solution was concentrated. Yield: 33 mg white solid (96 μmol, 78.82%)

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 2.48 (dd, *J* = 7.63, 2.67 Hz, 1 H), 2.52 - 2.60 (m, 1 H), 2.76 (dd, *J* = 13.92, 9.73 Hz, 1 H), 2.88 (t, *J* = 2.67 Hz, 1 H), 3.04 (dd, *J* = 13.92, 4.39 Hz, 1 H), 3.70 - 3.82 (m, 2 H), 4.33 (td, *J* = 7.82, 6.10 Hz, 1 H), 4.62 (ddd, *J* = 9.73, 8.39, 4.39 Hz, 1 H), 7.17 - 7.20 (m, 1 H), 7.20 - 7.23 (m, 1 H), 7.23 - 7.27 (m, 4 H), 7.35 (s, 1 H), 8.36 (dd, *J* = 8.20, 5.53 Hz, 2 H);

¹³C NMR-BB (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.78 (s, 1 C), 37.70 (s, 1 C), 50.51 (s, 1 C), 51.48 (s, 1 C), 53.91 (s, 1 C), 73.09 (s, 1 C), 80.61 (s, 1 C), 126.36 (s, 1 C), 128.10 (s, 2 C), 129.25 (s, 2 C), 137.58 (s, 1 C), 167.25 (s, 1 C), 170.80 (s, 1 C), 171.37 (s, 1 C);

¹³C NMR-DEPT (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.78 (s, 1 C), 37.70 (s, 1 C), 50.51 (s, 1 C), 51.48 (s, 1 C), 53.91 (s, 1 C), 73.09 (s, 1 C), 80.61 (s, 1 C), 126.36 (s, 1 C), 128.10 (s, 2 C), 129.25 (s, 2 C);

MS ES+ *m/z* = 343.229 [M+H]⁺, 365.216 [M+Na]⁺ (C₁₆H₁₈N₆O₃).

3.4.2 Cyclo-1,4-Triazol[-β-Ala-Phe-Pra]-NH₂ (17)

H-β-Ala-Phe-Pra-NH₂×TFA (9):

Figure 3.120: ¹H-NMR of H-β-Ala-Phe-Pra-NH₂×TFA (9)

Figure 3.121: ^{13}C -NMR-BB (top) and ^{13}C -NMR-DEPT (bottom) of $H\text{-}\beta\text{-Ala-Phe-Pra-NH}_2 \times \text{TFA}$ (**9**)

Compound delivered by Peptide Synthesis Laboratory:

¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 2.34 - 2.48 (m, 2 H), 2.52 - 2.64 (m, 2 H), 2.74 (dd, *J* = 13.67, 10.17 Hz, 1H), 2.84 - 2.90 (m, 3 H), 3.04 (dd, *J* = 13.67, 4.45 Hz, 1 H), 4.30 - 4.35 (m, 1 H), 4.56 - 4.61 (m, 1 H), 7.16 - 7.23 (m, 2 H), 7.26 (d, *J* = 4.45 Hz, 4 H), 7.38 (s, 1 H), 7.67 (br s, 3 H), 8.25 (d, *J* = 7.95 Hz, 1 H), 8.42 (d, *J* = 8.27 Hz, 1 H);

¹³C NMR-BB (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.81 (s, 1 C), 31.94 (s, 1 C), 35.28 (s, 1 C), 37.61 (s, 1 C), 51.38 (s, 1 C), 54.00 (s, 1 C), 73.04 (s, 1 C), 80.58 (s, 1 C), 126.30 (s, 1 C), 128.05 (s, 2 C), 129.22 (s, 2 C), 137.80 (s, 1 C), 157.46 - 158.43 (m, 1 C), 169.38 (s, 1 C), 171.07 (s, 1 C), 171.36 (s, 1 C);

¹³C NMR DEPT (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.81 (s, 1 C), 31.94 (s, 1 C), 35.28 (s, 1 C), 37.61 (s, 1 C), 51.38 (s, 1 C), 54.00 (s, 1 C), 126.30 (s, 1 C), 128.05 (s, 2 C), 129.22 (s, 2 C);

MS ES+ *m/z* = 331.247 [*M*+H]⁺ (C₁₇H₂₂N₄O₅).

Azido-β-Ala-Phe-Pra-NH₂ (13):

Figure 3.122: ¹H-NMR of Azido-β-Ala-Phe-Pra-NH₂ (13)

Figure 3.123: ^{13}C -NMR-BB (top) and ^{13}C -NMR-DEPT (bottom) of Azido- β -Ala-Phe-Pra- NH_2 (**13**)

H-β-Ala-Phe-Pra-NH₂ x TFA (**9**) (1 eq, 50 mg, 112 μmol) was dissolved in NaHCO₃ (7 eq, 3.96 ml, 200 mM aq.) and ISAxH₂SO₄ (2.5 eq, 563 μl, 500 mM aq.) and copper(II)sulfate pentahydrate (0.01 eq, 56.2 μl, 20 mM aq.) was added. The reaction was stirred for 16 h at room and resulted in formation of a precipitate. The reaction was controlled by LC-MS. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and dissolved in methanol. The LC-MS showed clean product (**13**). The solution was concentrated. Yield: 39.1 mg white solid (110 μmol, 98.21%)

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 2.30 - 2.40 (m, 2 H) 2.51 - 2.63 (m, 2 H) 2.75 (dd, *J* = 13.73, 9.92 Hz, 1 H) 2.86 (t, *J* = 2.67 Hz, 1 H) 3.03 (dd, *J* = 14.11, 4.58 Hz, 1 H) 3.39 (t, *J* = 6.48 Hz, 2 H) 4.28 - 4.34 (m, 1 H) 4.58 (ddd, *J* = 9.63, 8.30, 4.58 Hz, 1 H) 7.15 - 7.20 (m, 1 H) 7.20 - 7.23 (m, 1 H) 7.25 (d, *J* = 4.20 Hz, 4 H) 7.32 (s, 1 H) 8.17 (d, *J* = 8.01 Hz, 1 H) 8.29 (d, *J* = 8.01 Hz, 1 H);

¹³C NMR-BB (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.75 (s, 1 C), 34.38 (s, 1 C), 37.52 (s, 1 C), 46.86 (s, 1 C), 51.37 (s, 1 C), 53.95 (s, 1 C), 73.05 (s, 1 C), 80.53 (s, 1 C), 126.25 (s, 1 C), 128.01 (s, 2 C), 129.19 (s, 2 C), 137.79 (s, 1 C), 169.51 (s, 1 C), 171.07 (s, 1 C), 171.36 (s, 1 C);

¹³C NMR-DEPT (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.75 (s, 1 C) 34.38 (s, 1 C) 37.52 (s, 1 C) 46.86 (s, 1 C) 51.37 (s, 1 C) 53.95 (s, 1 C) 73.05 (s, 1 C) 80.53 (s, 1 C) 126.25 (s, 1 C) 128.01 (s, 2 C) 129.19 (s, 2 C);

MS ES+ *m/z* = 357.248 [*M*+H]⁺, 379.235 [*M*+Na]⁺ (C₁₇H₂₀N₆O₃).

Cyclo-1,4-Triazol[β -Ala-Phe-Pra]-NH₂ (17):

Figure 3.124: ¹H-NMR of Cyclo-1,4-Triazol[β -Ala-Phe-Pra]-NH₂ (17)

Figure 3.125: ¹³C-NMR-BB (top) and ¹³C-NMR-DEPT (bottom) of Cyclo-1,4-Triazol[β -Ala-Phe-Pra]-NH₂ (**17**)

Azido- β -Ala-Phe-Pra-NH₂ (**13**) (20 mg, 112 μ mol) was added to ethanol (3.6 ml). To this suspension was added CuSO₄·5H₂O (0.2 eq, 112 μ l, 200 mM aq.) and L-sodium ascorbate (673 μ l, 0.3 eq, 50 mM aq.). The reaction was stirred for 16 h at room temperature and resulted in formation of a precipitate. The reaction was controlled by LC-MS. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and methanol. The filtrate was dissolved in DMSO and was purified with preparative HPLC. Yield: 6 mg white solid (16.8 μ mol, 15.00%).

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 2.20 - 2.28 (m, 1 H), 2.52 - 2.73 (m, 4 H), 2.84 (dd, *J* = 13.73, 6.48 Hz, 1 H), 3.17 (dd, *J* = 13.92, 4.77 Hz, 1 H), 4.34 (ddd, *J* = 12.21, 9.54, 4.96 Hz, 1 H), 4.43 - 4.52 (m, 2 H), 4.61 (ddd, *J* = 13.45, 5.44, 1.34 Hz, 1 H), 7.12 - 7.18 (m, 4 H), 7.19 - 7.25 (m, 3 H), 7.54 (s, 1 H), 7.98 (br d, *J* = 9.54 Hz, 1 H), 8.01 (d, *J* = 9.92 Hz, 1 H);

¹³C NMR-BB (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 27.62 (s, 1 C), 36.30 (s, 1 C), 37.46 (s, 1 C), 47.10 (s, 1 C), 51.68 (s, 1 C), 53.07 (s, 1 C), 126.17 (s, 1 C), 126.73 (s, 1 C), 128.08 (s, 2 C), 128.98 (s, 2 C), 137.83 (s, 1 C), 141.93 (s, 1 C), 168.98 (s, 1 C), 170.63 (s, 1 C), 172.67 (s, 1 C);

¹³C NMR-DEPT (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 27.62 (s, 1 C), 36.30 (s, 1 C), 37.46 (s, 1 C), 47.10 (s, 1 C), 51.68 (s, 1 C), 53.07 (s, 1 C), 126.17 (s, 1 C), 126.73 (s, 1 C), 128.08 (s, 1 C), 128.98 (s, 1 C);

MS ES+ *m/z* = 357.237 [*M*+H]⁺ (C₁₇H₂₂N₆O₃).

3.4.3 Cyclo-1,4-Triazol[-2-Abz-Phe-Pra]-OH (18)

H-2-Abz-Pra-OH×TFA (10):

Figure 3.126: ¹H-NMR of H-2-Abz-Pra-OH×TFA (10)

Figure 3.127: ^{13}C -NMR-BB (top) and ^{13}C -NMR-DEPT (bottom) of H-2-Abz-Pra-OHxTFA (**10**)

¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 1.27 (s, 1 H), 2.62 - 2.70 (m, 2 H), 2.92 (t, *J* = 2.54 Hz, 1 H), 2.98 (dd, *J* = 13.67, 11.13 Hz, 1 H), 3.13 (dd, *J* = 13.83, 3.66 Hz, 1 H), 4.37 - 4.42 (m, 1 H), 4.72 - 4.78 (m, 1 H), 6.57 (t, *J* = 7.31 Hz, 1 H), 6.70 (d, *J* = 7.95 Hz, 1 H), 7.11 - 7.21 (m, 2 H), 7.26 (t, *J* = 7.47 Hz, 2 H), 7.37 (d, *J* = 6.99 Hz, 2 H), 7.49 (dd, *J* = 7.95, 1.27 Hz, 1 H), 8.32 (d, *J* = 8.06 Hz, 1 H), 8.48 (d, *J* = 7.95 Hz, 1 H);

¹³C NMR-BB (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.16 (s, 1 C), 30.70 (s, 1 C), 37.11 (s, 1 C), 51.10 (s, 1 C), 54.28 (s, 1 C), 73.37 (s, 1 C), 80.26 (s, 1 C), 115.33 (d, *J* = 45.56 Hz, 1 C), 116.91 (s, 1 C), 126.22 (s, 1 C), 128.04 (s, 2 C), 128.44 (s, 1 C), 129.21 (s, 2 C), 131.90 (s, 1 C), 138.43 (s, 1 C), 148.11 (s, 1 C), 158.24 (q, *J* = 36.91 Hz, 1 C), 168.45 (s, 1 C), 171.66 (s, 1 C), 171.77 (s, 1 C);

¹³C NMR-DEPT (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.16 (s, 1 C), 30.70 (s, 1 C), 37.11 (s, 1 C), 51.10 (s, 1 C), 54.28 (s, 1 C), 116.91 (s, 1 C), 126.22 (s, 1 C), 128.04 (s, 2 C), 128.44 (s, 1 C), 129.21 (s, 2 C), 131.90 (s, 1 C);

MS ES+ *m/z* = 380.241 [*M*+*H*]⁺ (C₂₁H₂₁N₃O₄).

Azido-2-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH (14):

Figure 3.128: ¹H-NMR of Azido-2-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH (14)

Figure 3.129: ^{13}C -NMR-BB (top) and ^{13}C -NMR-DEPT (bottom) of Azido-2-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH (**14**)

H-2-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH x TFA (**10**) (1 eq, 50 mg, 101 μ mol) was dissolved in NaHCO₃ (7 eq, 3.55 ml, 200 mM aq.) and ISAxH₂SO₄ (2.5 eq, 506 μ l, 500 mM aq.) and copper(II)sulfate pentahydrate (0.01 eq, 56.2 μ l, 20 mM aq.) was added. The reaction was stirred for 16 h at room temperature and resulted in formation of a precipitate. The reaction was controlled by LC-MS. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and dissolved in methanol. The solution was concentrated, dissolved in DMSO and was purified with preparative HPLC. Yield: 34.2 mg white solid (84.4 μ mol, 83.25%)

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 2.62 - 2.70 (m, 2H), 2.91 (dd, *J*=13.92, 10.11Hz, 1H), 2.94 (t, *J*=2.48Hz, 1H), 3.13 - 3.19 (m, 1H), 4.38 - 4.45 (m, 1H), 4.77 (ddd, *J*=10.11, 8.39, 4.01Hz, 1H), 7.18 - 7.24 (m, 2H), 7.25 - 7.31 (m, 2H), 7.31 - 7.37 (m, 3H), 7.42 (dd, *J*=7.63, 1.53Hz, 1H), 7.51 (t, *J*=7.70Hz, 1H), 8.42 (d, *J*=7.63Hz, 1H), 8.49 (d, *J*=8.39Hz, 1H), 13.04 (br s, 1H);

¹³C NMR-BB (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.29 (s, 1C), 37.28 (s, 1C), 51.10 (s, 1C), 54.47 (s, 1C), 73.42 (s, 1C), 80.09 (s, 1C), 119.56 (s, 1C), 124.82 (s, 1C), 126.34 (s, 1C), 127.43 (s, 1C), 127.94 (s, 2C), 129.41 (s, 2C), 129.79 (s, 1C), 131.67 (s, 1C), 136.71 (s, 1C), 137.77 (s, 1C), 164.98 (s, 1C), 171.00 (s, 1C), 171.56 (s, 1C);

¹³C NMR (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.29 (s, 1C), 37.28 (s, 1C), 51.10 (s, 1C), 54.47 (s, 1C), 73.42 (s, 1C), 119.56 (s, 1C), 124.82 (s, 1C), 126.34 (s, 1C), 127.94 (s, 1C), 129.41 (s, 1C), 129.79 (s, 1C), 131.67 (s, 1C);

MS ES+ *m/z*=406.243 [*M*+H]⁺ *m/z*=428.229 [*M*+Na]⁺ (C₂₁H₁₉N₅O₄).

Cyclo-1,4-Triazol[-2-Abz-Phe-Pra]-OH (18):

Figure 3.130: ¹H-NMR of Cyclo-1,4-Triazol[-2-Abz-Phe-Pra]-OH (18)

Figure 3.131: ^{13}C -NMR-BB (top) and ^{13}C -NMR-DEPT (bottom) of Cyclo-1,4-Triazol[2-Abz-Phe-Pra]-OH (**18**)

Azido-2-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH (**14**) (20 mg, 49.3 μmol) was added to ethanol (1.6 ml). To this suspension was added $\text{CuSO}_4 \times 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.2 eq, 49. μl , 200 mM aq.) and L-sodium ascorbate (296 μl , 0.3 eq, 50 mM aq.). The reaction was stirred for 16 h at room temperature and resulted in formation of a precipitate. The reaction was controlled by LC-MS. The precipitate was filtered, washed with 0.5 M HCl and methanol and dried. The filtrate was clean product (**18**). Yield: 6.7 mg white solid (16.5 μmol , 33.50%).

^1H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ ppm 2.65 - 2.72 (m, 1 H), 2.83 - 2.94 (m, 2 H), 3.27 - 3.32 (m, 1 H), 4.49 (ddd, $J = 11.83, 9.73, 4.77$ Hz, 1 H), 4.62 - 4.68 (m, 1 H), 7.15 - 7.22 (m, 3 H), 7.22 - 7.31 (m, 4 H), 7.55 (t, $J = 7.64$ Hz, 1 H), 7.66 (td, $J = 7.82, 1.53$ Hz, 1 H), 7.80 (d, $J = 7.25$ Hz, 1 H), 7.87 (s, 1 H), 8.27 - 8.36 (m, 1 H), 8.48 (d, $J = 9.92$ Hz, 1 H), 12.89 (br s, 1 H);

^{13}C NMR-BB (151 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ ppm 27.85 (s, 1 C), 36.14 (s, 1 C), 50.98 (s, 1 C), 53.92 (s, 1 C), 123.83 (s, 1 C), 125.70 (s, 1 C), 126.28 (s, 1 C), 127.84 (s, 1 C), 128.08 (s, 2 C), 129.13 (s, 2 C), 129.23 (s, 1 C), 130.54 (s, 1 C), 132.68 (s, 1 C), 133.67 (s, 1 C), 137.66 (s, 1 C), 142.37 (s, 1 C), 165.72 (s, 1 C), 169.35 (s, 1 C), 172.16 (s, 1 C);

^{13}C NMR-DEPT (151 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ ppm 27.85 (s, 1 C), 36.14 (s, 1 C), 50.98 (s, 1 C), 53.92 (s, 1 C), 123.83 (s, 1 C), 125.70 (s, 1 C), 126.28 (s, 1 C), 127.84 (s, 1 C), 128.08 (s, 2 C), 129.13 (s, 2 C), 129.23 (s, 1 C), 130.54 (s, 1 C);

MS ES+ $m/z = 406.244$ [$M+H$] $^+$ ($\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4$).

3.4.4 Cyclo-1,4-Triazol-[-3-Abz-Phe-Pra]-OH (19):

H-3-Abz-Pra-OH×TFA (11):

Figure 3.132: ¹H-NMR of H-3-Abz-Pra-OH×TFA (11)

Figure 3.133: ^{13}C -NMR-BB (top) and ^{13}C -NMR-DEPT (bottom) of H-3-Abz-Pra-OHxTFA (**11**)

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 2.63 - 2.67 (m, 2 H), 2.91 (t, *J* = 2.67 Hz, 1 H), 2.98 (dd, *J* = 13.73, 10.68 Hz, 1 H), 3.13 (dd, *J* = 13.73, 3.81 Hz, 1 H), 4.37 - 4.41 (m, 1 H), 4.78 (ddd, *J* = 10.97, 8.68, 3.62 Hz, 1 H), 6.98 (br d, *J* = 7.25 Hz, 1 H), 7.13 - 7.18 (m, 1 H), 7.23 - 7.29 (m, 5 H), 7.36 (d, *J* = 7.25 Hz, 2 H), 8.47 (br d, *J* = 8.77 Hz, 1 H), 8.50 (d, *J* = 8.01 Hz, 1 H);

¹³C NMR-BB (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.14 (s, 1 C), 37.15 (s, 1 C), 40.08 (s, 1 C), 51.10 (s, 1 C), 54.56 (s, 1 C), 73.35 (s, 1 C), 80.25 (s, 1 C), 116.02 (d, *J* = 293.73 Hz, 1 C), 116.30 - 116.79 (m, 1 C), 118.88 - 119.52 (m, 1 C), 119.81 - 120.53 (m, 1 C), 126.23 (s, 1 C), 128.03 (s, 2 C), 129.04 (s, 1 C), 129.22 (s, 2 C), 135.18 (s, 1 C), 138.32 (s, 1 C), 141.31 - 143.16 (m, 1 C), 158.20 (q, *J* = 35.18 Hz, 1 C), 166.15 (s, 1 C), 171.58 (s, 1 C), 171.62 (s, 1 C);

¹³C NMR-DEPT (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.14 (s, 1 C), 33.01 (s, 1 C), 33.60 (s, 1 C), 37.15 (s, 1 C), 51.10 (s, 1 C), 54.56 (s, 1 C), 73.35 (s, 1 C), 80.25 (s, 1 C), 116.37 - 116.90 (m, 1 C), 118.99 - 119.47 (m, 1 C), 120.00 - 120.39 (m, 1 C), 126.23 (s, 1 C), 128.03 (s, 2 C), 129.04 (s, 1 C), 129.22 (s, 2 C);

MS ES+ *m/z* = 380.241 [*M*+H]⁺ (C₂₁H₂₁N₃O₄).

Azido-3-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH (15):

Figure 3.134: ¹H-NMR of Azido-3-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH (15)

Figure 3. 135: ¹³C-NMR-BB (top) and ¹³C-NMR-DEPT (bottom) of Azido-3-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH (**15**)

H-3-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH x TFA (**11**) (1 eq, 300 mg, 608 μ mol) was dissolved in NaHCO₃ (7 eq, 21.2 ml, 200 mM aq.) and ISAxH₂SO₄ (2.5 eq, 3.04 ml, 500 mM aq.) and copper(II)sulfate pentahydrate (0.01 eq, 304 μ l, 20 mM aq.) was added. The reaction was stirred for 16 h at room temperature and resulted in formation of a precipitate. The reaction was controlled by LC-MS. The precipitate was filtered and was purified with preparative HPLC. Yield (**15**): 164 mg white solid (384 μ mol, 63.211%)

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 2.61 - 2.69 (m, 2 H), 2.92 (t, *J* = 2.48 Hz, 1 H), 2.97 (dd, *J* = 13.54, 11.25 Hz, 1 H), 3.15 (dd, *J* = 13.73, 3.43 Hz, 1 H), 4.36 - 4.41 (m, 1 H), 4.79 - 4.84 (m, 1 H), 7.13 - 7.19 (m, 1 H), 7.22 - 7.27 (m, 3 H), 7.38 (d, *J* = 7.25 Hz, 2 H), 7.46 - 7.50 (m, 2 H), 7.58 (d, *J* = 7.59 Hz, 1 H), 8.54 (d, *J* = 7.63 Hz, 1 H), 8.74 (d, *J* = 8.77 Hz, 1 H), 12.95 (br s, 1 H);

¹³C NMR-BB (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.08 (s, 1 C), 37.18 (s, 1 C), 51.17 (s, 1 C), 54.66 (s, 1 C), 73.35 (s, 1 C), 80.34 (s, 1 C), 117.91 (s, 1 C), 121.95 (s, 1 C), 124.18 (s, 1 C), 126.27 (s, 1 C), 128.06 (s, 2 C), 129.22 (s, 2 C), 129.99 (s, 1 C), 135.80 (s, 1 C), 138.33 (s, 1 C), 139.56 (s, 1 C), 165.28 (s, 1 C), 171.51 (s, 1 C), 171.64 (s, 1 C);

¹³C NMR-DEPT (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm 21.08 (s, 1 C), 37.18 (s, 1 C), 51.17 (s, 1 C), 54.66 (s, 1 C), 73.35 (s, 1 C), 117.91 (s, 1 C), 121.95 (s, 1 C), 124.18 (s, 1 C), 126.27 (s, 1 C), 128.06 (s, 2 C), 129.22 (s, 2 C), 129.99 (s, 1 C);

MS ES+ *m/z* = 406.243 [*M*+H]⁺ *m/z* = 428.229 [*M*+Na]⁺ (C₂₁H₁₉N₅O₄).

Cyclo-1,4-Triazol-[-3-Abz-Phe-Pra]-OH (19):

Figure 3.136: ¹H-NMR of Cyclo-1,4-Triazol-[-3-Abz-Phe-Pra]-OH

Azido-3-Abz-Phe-Pra-OH (**15**) (20 mg, 49.3 μmol) was added to DMSO (1 ml) and Borate buffer (1 ml, 500 mM), added $\text{CuSO}_4 \times 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 eq, 247 μl , 200 mM aq.), L-sodium ascorbate (247 μl , 1 eq, 50 mM aq.) and TBTA (247 μl , 1 eq, 200mM in DMSO). The reaction was stirred for 16 h at room temperature and resulted in formation of a precipitate. The reaction was controlled by LC-MS. The precipitate was filtered, washed with 0,5 M HCl and DMSO. The mother liquid was purified with preparative HPLC. Yield: 2 mg white solid (4.93 μmol , 10%).

^1H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ ppm 2.94 - 3.12 (m, 2 H) 3.15 - 3.26 (m, 1 H) 3.31 (br s, 1 H) 4.54 (br s, 1 H) 4.69 - 4.88 (m, 1 H) 7.08 - 7.20 (m, 1 H) 7.23 (br s, 2 H) 7.37 (br d, $J = 6.10$ Hz, 2 H) 7.60 (t, $J = 8.01$ Hz, 1 H) 7.90 - 8.10 (m, 2 H) 8.25 - 8.44 (m, 2 H) 8.87 (br d, $J = 7.63$ Hz, 2 H) 12.65 - 13.38 (m, 1 H);

MS ES+ $m/z = 406.262$ $[M+H]^+$, 811.513 $[2M+H]^+$ ($\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4$).